

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS ERIC Catalogue of Services User Guidelines

Version n. 1, 27 June 2025

Call for Access n. 1: 30 June 2025 – 30 September 2025

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INTRODUCTION TO E-RIHS CATALOGUE OF SERVICES (CoS)

The E-RIHS Catalogue of Services (CoS) is the single-entry point for accessing the four E-RIHS service platforms:

- **MOLAB** for in situ, non-invasive analysis using portable equipment
- **FIXLAB** for access to large-scale, stationary analytical facilities
- **ARCHLAB** for access to curated scientific archives and sample collections
- **DIGILAB** for access to digital tools.

Access is granted through competitive peer-reviewed calls for access.

These guidelines explain how to create a user account, submit an access application, and follow the process from selection to post-access reporting.

1. CREATE AN ACCOUNT

To access the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services (CoS), you need a personal user account.

- Go to <http://catalogue.e-rihs.eu/> and click on "Sign in" (top right)
- Log in with your ORCID account (correct your contact e-mail!) or create an E-RIHS account
- Activate your account through the verification link you will receive
- Complete your personal profile with your professional background, institutional affiliation*, and a short CV.

*For more details on adding your organization, see the FAQ section.

2. USER DASHBOARD

Upon logging in, you access your personal user dashboard, the main interface for managing your activity in the E-RIHS CoS.

From the dashboard, you can:

- Update your profile
- Browse the CoS
- Select services in the CoS to be added to an application
- Compile and submit a single- or multi-service application for one or more of the E-RIHS platforms
- Monitor the status of your applications as User Group Leader (UGL) or Team Member (TM) in the 'List of Applications' (e.g., in review or awaiting feasibility)
- Download the application as PDF, view the application history, and upload upon request related files such as ownership or permissions
- Create and submit a post access report once access is completed.

3. SUBMIT AN ACCESS APPLICATION

SELECT YOUR SERVICES

During an open call, registered users can log in to the CoS, browse and select available services, and submit an online application for access.

Before selecting services, users are strongly encouraged to read the full description of each service carefully, to ensure its relevance and suitability for their research. Kindly check the full list of services, as multiple options are available.

Services selected must be:

- Technically appropriate for the intended research
- Clearly aligned with the project's objectives.

If any doubt arises regarding a service's scope, or compatibility with the project, users are urged to contact the Service Manager indicated in the webpage of the service or the E-RIHS User Helpdesk at helpdesk@e-rihs.eu.

CREATE AND SUBMIT THE APPLICATION

You can create an access application directly from your dashboard. It can be saved as a draft and submitted once completed.

The application must include:

- Project title and acronym
- Type of application: new, long-term or resubmission
- Requested platforms: select one or more (e.g. ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB) and provide details of each object, sample, site etc.
- Detailed scientific description of project including:
 - Project summary (300 words)
 - Scientific background (500 words)
 - Description of the planned work and Analytical Methods (600 words)
 - Previous analyses of the item (300 words)
 - Expected achievements (400 words)
 - Impact and dissemination plan (400 words)
 - Data management plan (300 words)
 - References (min. 5, max. 10)
 - Research disciplines (see FAQ section for guidance)
- Upload additional documents if required.
- User group details: all members of the user group must be registered in the CoS to be inserted into an application. The User Group Leader (UGL) may appoint a deputy who will also receive application-related communications.

Note: The User Group Leader can submit only 1 application per call and cannot submit another in that role until the granted access is

completed. For any successive applications, they may still be included as team member.

- Read and accept the terms and conditions.
- All personal data provided through the application process will be processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), as described in the [E-RIHS Data Management Policy](#).
- Verify and confirm the submission. The system will indicate whether the application has been accepted for the evaluation phase.

4. EVALUATION

TIMELINE

ELIGIBILITY

- The application must comply with the [E-RIHS Access Policy](#) and include a Data Management Plan in accordance with the [E-RIHS Data Management Policy](#).
- The application must support E-RIHS's vision and mission, as well as with scientific, technical, and ethical standards.
- The application must be written in English.
- The application must include at least one service available in the Catalogue of Services.
- All required documents must be uploaded and complete.

Applications that fail to meet any of these criteria will be considered ineligible and excluded from evaluation.

FEASIBILITY

Once the application is submitted, the Service Manager(s) of selected service(s) carry out the feasibility check, according to the following criteria:

- Risk to object: Are condition, handling, and analytical risks (e.g. light, radiation) addressed?
- Implementation plan and timeline: Is the timeline feasible and detailed, with service availability and logistical needs (e.g., space, equipment) considered?
- Health and safety risks: Are risks to users and providers identified and addressed (e.g., toxic substances, physical hazards)?

If the application is not feasible or partially feasible, the user will be notified by e-mail and may revise the application – but only until the call deadline. If the application is submitted at the call deadline, no modifications will be possible.

At the call deadline, applications already marked as feasible retain that status, while applications not yet evaluated undergo feasibility check.

EVALUATION BY PEER-REVIEW PANEL

Applications that pass the feasibility check are evaluated by an independent international Peer Review Panel (PRP).

Reviewers assess the quality of each proposal based on the following criteria:

Excellence

- Relevance of the research questions: Are the questions significant and likely to advance object/site understanding, heritage science, or related fields?
- Methodology and research plan: Are the methods appropriate, clearly described, and robust enough to address the research questions?
- Originality: How novel and innovative is the proposed research?
- Expertise of user group: Is the user group's expertise relevant, sufficient, and multidisciplinary to ensure research success?
- Timeliness: Relevance to current issues and advancements in heritage science.
- State of the art: Complete, relevant, quality research background; key past studies cited; project builds clearly on previous work.

Impact

- Research community impact: Importance and significance of the issue; expected outcomes for the specialized community.
- Knowledge sharing: Plans to publish and disseminate results broadly, reaching all relevant interdisciplinary communities.
- Innovation potential: Degree of innovation (e.g., high-risk, high-gain); potential to open new avenues in heritage science or multidisciplinary heritage knowledge.
- Open access: Commitment and plans for managing, archiving, and documenting data to ensure accessibility and transparency for future reuse.
- Expected impacts on society or industry: Anticipated positive societal and economic effects, including cultural heritage awareness, education, and industry benefits.

APPLICATION RANKING

Applications are ranked according to their final evaluation score and allocated based on the availability of the requested services.

The ranking is established using weighted criteria:

- **Excellence – 60%**
- **Impact – 20%**
- **Feasibility – 20%**

Based on the ranking and service capacity, each application will result in one of the following outcomes:

Granted access – selected and assigned to the requested service(s)

Reserve list – eligible, pending availability of requested service(s)

Rejected – not retained for access.

Applicants are notified by e-mail.

5. ACCESS OFFER

If access is granted, the Helpdesk and Service Manager prepare a formal access offer. The user must accept the offer (communications by e-mail) and upload any outstanding permissions before the access can take place.

Access that has been granted must be carried out within 12 calendar months.

During the access, users will receive technical support and, where relevant, training from E-RIHS staff, in full respect of the collaboration and knowledge-sharing principles that E-RIHS promotes.

6. POST-ACCESS DUTIES

Once all access activities related to the project are completed, the user must submit the following within 2 months:

- Access report (available in the dashboard)
- User satisfaction survey.

Both are required to fulfil post-access duties and archive the project.

FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS (FAQ)

How do I insert my organization?

The field “organizations” is linked to ROR (Research Organization Registry). If your organization is registered in ROR, it will automatically appear as you begin typing, displayed in the language in which it was officially registered. If your organization is not listed, you will need to manually enter its full name and provide any additional identifying details (such as country and department) as requested in the form.

Can I submit an application without being affiliated with an institution?

Yes, users can submit applications independently, even without involving an institution.

How many applications can a User Group Leader submit?

The User Group Leader can submit only 1 application per call and cannot submit another in that role until the granted access is completed. For any successive applications, they may still be included as team member.

What is the purpose of the “Research Disciplines” field in the online application and how should I choose the appropriate options?

This field is used to assign the most suitable Peer Review Panelists to your application. Please select only the disciplines most relevant to the core scientific content and methodology of your application. Multiple choices are allowed, but accuracy is essential to ensure proper evaluation. Available disciplines include:

- Chemistry
- Earth Sciences & Environment
- Energy
- Engineering and Technology
- Humanities
- Information and Communication Technologies
- Life Sciences and Biotech
- Material Science
- Mathematics
- Physics
- Social Sciences

Where can I check the status of my application?

You can track the status of your application directly in the Application section of your dashboard.

Can I edit my application after submission?

If your application is marked as not feasible or partially feasible, you can modify it only until the call closes. Once the call is officially closed, you cannot modify your application.

What happens if my application is not feasible?

You will be notified, and you may have the option to revise your application and/or choose different services before the call deadline. If an application is not feasible following the call deadline, it will not undergo further assessment.

Is it mandatory to submit a post-access report?

Yes, the User Group Leader must submit the report within 2 months after all accesses have been carried out. You can access this from your personal dashboard, post access reports section. Until these are delivered the dashboard will not permit the user to lead further applications.

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